

Enhancing the Sustainability of the Electronics in the Automotive Sector in the context of Circular Economy through a Decision-Making framework

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Abstract— The automotive industry is evolving towards a more circular and sustainable paradigm, driven by the increasing climate change concern and the European Commission's emphasis on critical raw materials (CRMs) recovery from automotive electronics. Currently, industry decision-makers focus on recovering key components for reusing purposes and specific materials, such as metals and plastics. Their approach is mostly addressing the economic benefits of recycling and meeting regulatory requirements, but often overlooking CRMs and other valuable materials lost in conventional shredding. The lack of methodologies advising on the economic feasibility, environmental and social impacts in electronic components disassembly and recycling is hindering the possibility to recover valuable and rare materials and to design more circular oriented components. This work introduces a comprehensive advisory framework designed to enhance product circularity and sustainability, specifically emphasizing the beginning (BoL) and end-of-life (EoL) of a product. It includes an innovative methodology to support the different actors along the automotive value chain in their decision-making process. This approach guides them through a structured and predefined decision-making flow, offering a range of tools and recommendations to facilitate the implementation of circularity and sustainability performance improvements in electronic components. The framework's effectiveness has been validated through the implementation of a software advisory module meant to support decision-making processes for various stakeholders, including car manufacturers and recycling experts. The methodology deployment and the interaction with the different stakeholders involved in the BoL and EoL phases provided useful information to confirm or reshape some of the methodology designed parts, considering criteria such as data availability. By implementing this framework, companies can adopt a comprehensive approach to incorporate circular practices and boost the sustainability of automotive electronics, positioning themselves at the forefront in the transition toward a more responsible global economy.

Keywords—Sustainability decision-making, Circularity decision-making, Advisory methodology, Circular Automotive, Design for recycling, Design for disassembly

IV. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, optimizing product performance throughout its life cycle with a focus on sustainability and circularity is essential for the automotive industry. Automotive companies must adhere to standards and regulations governing operations and outcomes. Directives at the European level, such as the ELV (End-of-Life Vehicles) Directive and REACH Regulation, emphasize waste management and product suitability [1], [2]. On the other hand, integrating sustainability and circularity into product development can enhance the strategic positioning of the company, leading to increased consumer demand and competitive advantage [3]. In general, pressure from institutions and stakeholders consistently drives the improvement of the sustainability of

products and processes and the transition towards a circular economy (CE) [4].

Expert guidance and appropriate tools are crucial for achieving sustainability and circularity goals. The term "advisory" refers to providing information, warnings, or assistance in decision-making. This can be done by human experts or advisory systems. These systems use knowledge from human experts, encoded for computer use, to evaluate solutions within a specific domain. They provide guidance through the decision-making process, but the final decision is typically made by the human. Collaboratively, the expert and the system identify and evaluate solutions iteratively [5].

In efforts to improve sustainability, the automotive manufacturers require support on implementing or modifying practices to achieve regulatory compliance and competitive advantage in their sector. These practices can be part of the Beginning (BoL) or the End of Life (EoL) phase of a product life cycle. Indeed, the design phase (at the BoL) proved to influence over 80% of the environmental impacts [6].

Concerning circularity targets, the automotive manufacturers typically look at the EoL phase to enhance product recovery [7]. Several strategies can be applied to enhance EoL recovery, but basically these follow two main approaches: curative or preventive. The first one focuses on the recovery process (optimizing disassembly or/and recycling processes), whereas the preventive one promotes recoverability through the product design. However, acting only with a curative approach may not be the right way, as not all the valuable material are currently extracted and recycled properly. Thus, manufacturers should incorporate circular strategies during the product design phase to ensure sustainability, including consideration of EoL aspects [8], [9].

Several advisory methodologies include the implementation of curative or preventive strategies to support EoL decision-making. Regarding the curative approach in the electronics sector, where e-waste management poses a growing challenge due to its volume and complexity [10], several tools have been developed to improve sorting and disassembling processes. With the ability to classify metallic fractions and non-metallic fractions from e-waste, [11] has facilitated efficient sorting processes for the recovery of valuable materials. Additionally, other advanced technology was developed to optimize recycling by allowing the identification and separation of different types of e-waste plastics [12]. The Refind Technologies developed by [13] is able to identify in whether EoL electronics are suitable for reuse, refurbishment or recycling, and sorts them, accordingly, increasing recovery rates in downstream processes. On the other hand, process simulation has shown potential for the evaluation of several recycling strategies and optimization, while providing environmental impact analysis [14], [15], [16]. However, there is a notable absence of

decision-making tools in the curative approach focused on electronic components within the automotive sector.

Regarding the preventive approach, numerous tools and methodologies have been developed to facilitate the creation of sustainable products in the context of the circular economy. These include the tools for Sustainability Conscious Design (SCD) and Recovery Conscious Design (RCD). The tools that implement SCD focus on improving the sustainability of a design throughout the entire product life cycle. The range of tools for SCD goes from basic and generic to more complex and quantitative tools that require a significant investment of time. Some tools conduct in-depth analyses, quantifying sustainability impacts and offering detailed solutions to improve a product's sustainability performance. On the contrary, many tools provide an initial qualitative analysis that produces broad recommendations for improvement. In general, these tools have been classified into four groups: guidelines/standards, checklists, comparative tools and analytical methods [17]. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is also considered an SCD tool and is one of the most common used [18].

On the other hand, RCD tools focus on maximizing and optimizing product recoverability. A relevant approach is the one developed by [8], which uses indices to assess the feasibility of each EoL scenario (reuse, remanufacture, recycling and incineration) of each design and examines preferred disassembly routes. [19] developed the EoL Scenario Evaluation Method (ELSEM), a multi-criteria decision-making tool used during the early design phase of product development. It helps designers to identify end-of-life scenarios that meet the company's commercial and environmental objectives and to determine the technical product characteristics for these scenarios and [20] developed an agent-based system for recycling-oriented eco-design, analysing parameters like material recyclability and disassembly costs.

Even though there are numerous strategies to aid decision-making during eco-design for enhancing either sustainability or circularity, there is a gap for the integration of both aspects. Furthermore, there is a deficiency in decision-making tools that integrate the three phases (disassembly, recycling, and eco-design) of the entire life cycle of electronic components. The present work addresses the above-mentioned critical gaps by offering a decision-making approach for circularity and sustainability within the automotive industry's electronics components. The Sustainability and Circularity (S&C) advisory framework proposed here offers a novel approach aimed at guiding decision-makers throughout the BoL and EoL of car Electronic Components (ECs), ensuring that their choices prioritize both sustainability and circularity principles.

V. METHODOLOGY

To overcome the challenges and critical issues described above, a methodology has been conceived to develop a sustainability and circularity advisory framework able to assist decision-makers in the automotive industry. The methodology consists of two main steps: the analysis of the current decision-making scenarios and the development of the S&C advisory framework. Through the interaction with selected stakeholders, for each of the three evaluated use cases, i.e., disassembly, recycling, and eco-design, the analysis of the current decision-making scenarios is performed (for sake of brevity AS IS decision-making analysis). The AS IS decision-

making analysis lays the foundation for the effective development of the sustainability and circularity advisory framework (for sake of brevity S&C advisory development). Besides the specific support for each use cases, the relationships between the three use cases are explored. Key decision-making outcomes that mutually influence each other in interconnected scenarios were identified and serve as an information link to facilitate integrated decision-making throughout the automotive lifecycle.

A. AS IS decision-making analysis

The first step of the methodology sets the stage for the effective development of the S&C advisory. The analysis of the current decision-making scenarios for disassembly, recycling, and design phases is meant to identify relevant decision-makers, key decisions, and existing gaps in providing support to decision-making. This analysis is conducted through dedicated interactions with stakeholders, including dismantlers, recyclers, car manufacturers, and sector experts, to gather information on current decision-making processes and outline the future ones evaluating potential advisory functionalities and user support.

The AS IS decision-making analysis comprises the following steps: (i) the identification of the stakeholders currently involved in the decision-making process; (ii) the identification of the types of decisions currently made by the stakeholders and the tools they employ for decision-making; and (iii) the identification of any existing gaps in terms of support needs.

It is worth to mention that, given the urgency of integrating sustainability and circularity perspectives into decision-making and at the same time given the rigidity of the automotive sector, the objective of the developed advisory framework is to enhance the current decision-making process without completely disrupting it. Therefore, the analysis has been driven by the goal of identifying critical issues and decisions needing support, extracting sector-specific decision rules to ensure the alignment of the advisory framework with existing decision drivers in automotive industry, specifically for the electronics segment.

B. S&C advisory development

The S&C advisory has been designed to support the identified decision-makers in the decision-making process by providing a structured series of suggestions and best practices. The decision-makers are guided in their decisions towards the implementation of sustainability and circularity performance enhancement by metrics tailored to support on the EoL and BoL of the car electronic components. To develop the S&C advisory entails for each use case: (i) the description of the decision-making process; (ii) the structuring of this process into a series of sequential decision moments; (iii) the definition of the metrics and tools to provide decision support, summarized into Decision Cards; (iv) the definition of an information flow diagram for each decision to determine the source of the inputs required by the S&C advisory. Specifically, for step (iii), each decision card details:

- Decisions to be made – clearly defining the decisions aids in identifying the precise nature of the problem or opportunity.
- Product focus on the decisions – specifying the object of the decision.

- Decision-maker – recognizing the decision-maker's profile, since different stakeholders may possess different expertise, priorities, and perspectives. Suggestions for additional supportive figures to assist the decision-maker may be provided.
- Required input – this encompasses necessary information, such as material mass, essential for calculating decision-making indicators.
- Supporting tools and technologies – listing available resources, including databases and simulation tools, from literature or other sources that aid in decision-making.
- Sustainability and Circularity indicators – incorporating environmental, social, economic, and circularity indicators is crucial for decision-making, offering a comprehensive view of the decision's impact. The complete list of indicators from which the indicators for each decision are selected is based on previous studies, currently submitted for publication [21].

Specifically, for step (iv), the inputs sources have been organized in three types: professional figures (e.g., component manufacturers, disassemblers), supporting tools (like sustainability tools), and external sources (e.g., literature, websites).

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The developed methodology is hereafter reported, encompassing the description of the AS IS decision-making analysis and S&C advisory development for the three use cases of automotive ECs in disassembly, recycling, and eco-design decision-making phases.

A. Analysis of automotive ECs AS IS decision-making

1) Disassembly AS IS scenario

Analysing the current scenario of decision-making during the disassembly phase of an ELV, it emerged that vehicles reaching dismantling facilities are treated by dismantling operators to separate the hazardous materials and recyclable components, according to the in-force EU directive on ELV [22]. The hazardous and recyclable materials are sent respectively to specialised disposal process and recycling plants. The remaining components of the vehicle are evaluated as “valuable to be disassembled” according to functioning status and to market demand. Considering specifically ECs, their disassembly path can be twofold. In the worst and most frequent case, they are discarded and shredded with the unrecoverable unvaluable components of the ELV. In some cases, they are extracted from the car to be resold as spare parts. However, even if it could be a promising alternative from the circularity perspective, selling EC for a second life cycle could be extremely challenging. The main issues preventing this circular practice are intrinsically related to the design of the components, which makes it difficult to extract them from the car without damaging them and at a sustainable cost for dismantlers, and to the risk of non-compliance with data privacy and quality, safety and warranty standards, as it is hard to verify the correct functioning of the component at EoL and the data formatting from previous use.

The critical gaps emerged from the analysis of the disassembly decision-making process includes the lack of information sharing among the car manufacturer and the

dismantlers regarding the position of components within the car, making difficult the extraction and the vehicle and the potential value embedded in them. The main driver for disassembly is purely associated to the economic cost of disassembly and potential return from selling materials or components, with little to no consideration for environmental aspects exception made for the constraints set by regulations. Currently, there are no regulations encouraging specifically the recycling of electronics from ELV). Additionally, there is a notable absence of market demand for electronic components, leading to their retention within scrap vehicles, which are later shredded.

2) Recycling AS IS scenario

The current recycling process in Europe involves the shredding of the vehicle with Printed Circuit Boards (PCBs) and other WEEE inside, as emerged from the AS IS scenario analysis for disassembly. The process consists of shredding, magnetic sorting, density and colour separation, and main metals recovery in foundries, such as steel and aluminium. The resulting efficiency of the recycling operations depends firstly on the efficiency of the recycling processing steps. At the state of the art of the recycling technology, tin, precious metal, such gold, silver, and palladium, and critical raw materials [23], such as copper and cobalt, are not always properly recovered and PCB fragments not always end up in the correct recycling stream. The efficiency is hindered by the failure to separate PCBs from vehicle, which leads to PCB particles contaminating the metal recovery process and makes their recovery difficult, as sorting them into the correct recycled fraction becomes a challenging task. To improve the recovery procedure, it is possible to act either downstream, optimizing the sorting process, or upstream, optimizing the disassembly process. In both cases, design and recovery are also involved in the recycling process. The downstream approach focuses on optimizing the design of the process to increase the possibilities of obtaining high-quality shredded fractions of PCBs, such as those containing only epoxy and valuable electronic components. Despite the potential assistance of colour sorting in the recovery process, the overall likelihood of recovery remains low due to significant PCB loss when attached to steel. Concerning the upstream process, if PCBs and WEEE are disassembled from the vehicle before the shredding process they can be sent immediately to the next disassembly process or to the right recycling process. Again, design plays a key role in facilitating disassembly and consequently recovery when acting of feature such as modularity and material compatibility.

The critical gaps emerged from the analysis of the recycling decision-making process include lack of prioritization of critical metal recovery over main metals and non-ferrous metals recovery, neglecting their potential value and impact from the sustainability perspective, and the lack of tool addressing the interconnection between depth of disassembly and recycling efficiency from one side, and sustainability and circularity from the other side.

3) Eco-design AS IS scenario

The design process is a fundamental step in the life cycle of a product as the decisions taken in this phase shape the product functional and sustainable behaviour along the through life cycle. In the design realm, boundaries are set by Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), as they provide product specifications and budget limitation to component manufacturers. Inside these boundaries, designers are free to

shape a product that meet both functional requirements and economic feasibility, while low expectation is envisaged for sustainability and circularity aspects in their design choices, exception made for those strictly regulated. Whether requirements such as the use of increased recycled content and of certified materials are considered, impacting the manufacturing process, raw material suppliers are also involved from the outset of decision-making. Still, among a plethora of alternative suppliers and design options, the main selection criterium adopted by OEMs is economical, i.e., chose the cheapest component that satisfies quality, safety, and functional requirements disregarding any sustainability considerations. Considering the impact design has on EoL behaviour of components, circularity approaches to design, such as design for disassembly (DfD) and design for recycling (DfR), are gaining relevance in the academia but still lack a structured support to implementation from an industrial perspective.

The critical gaps emerged from the analysis of the design decision-making process include lack of information on how to optimize board placement and component aggregation for easy disassembly; lack of support on preferable material choices and combination to enhance recycling performance; lack of a screening support to have visibility on the linkage between design setup and EoL behaviour.

B. S&C Advisory Framework

One of the main findings from the AS IS analysis is the intrinsic connection between the disassembly and recycling phases. Indeed, the disassembly procedure followed for a component significantly influences the quantity and the quality of the material extracted [24]. For this reason, these two phases are treated as a single use case during the implementation of the methodology, where this consideration is crucial in defining the sequence of the decisions and their interconnected influence.

1) Disassembly and Recycling Advisory

The development of the S&C advisory starts from the definition of key decision-making moments. The decisions and the sequence have been defined considering the outcomes of the AS IS analysis, in particular the link between disassembly routes and recycling efficiency. Key decision-making moments at the BoL that lack sustainability and circularity support include: (i) the selection of the components to be extracted from the car, according to both economic and environmental criteria; (ii) the definition of the most cost-effective disassembly path to be followed to extract the component from the car; (iii) the identification of the most sustainable combination of disassembly and recycling processes of the EC to maximise material recovery and sustainability benefits.

Fig. 1. Decision-making flow of Disassembly and Recycling phases

The above-mentioned decisions moments outline the decision-making flow, illustrated in Fig. 1, for the disassembly and recycling use case. A detailed description of the decision moments is hereafter provided, enriched with the definition of the S&C advisory support.

Decision-making moment 0. The first two key decision-making moments of the S&C advisory aims to identify one or more of ECs to be extracted from the vehicle. Decision 0 is not supported by the S&C advisory, but it is propaedeutic to the methodology. It prioritizes the selection of the components that can be resold as spare parts, i.e., priority is given to reuse over recycling. This decision is oriented to the implementation of non-destructive dismantling, promoting component and subassembly recovery over material recovery, practice that is preferable to recycling in terms of sustainability and circularity because it requires fewer transformation processes [25]. The car disassembly manager, which is the decision-maker, with support from an operator and a market analyst, analyses the vehicle using CAD models or expertise if CAD is unavailable. Subsequently, the disassembly operator verifies that the expected components are present in the vehicle and in which status, while the market analyst assesses market demand for spare parts estimating the revenue that can be obtained from their resale. Regulatory constraints regarding component reuse, particularly those related to safety, privacy, quality, and warranty are obviously binding the final decision. With input from the operator market analyst, determines which components is valuable to extract.

Decision-making moment 1. The decision-making moment 1 instead involves identifying which ECs is beneficial to extract from the vehicle under both the environmental and economic perspective. The decision considers destructive disassembly approach, i.e., a technique mainly concentrated on material recovery rather than parts recovery and reuse [24]. The decision-making process requires the collaboration among several key stakeholders, including the car disassembly manager, a sustainability expert, an accounting expert, and the disassembly operator. Initially, the disassembly manager and operator identify the remaining ECs in the vehicle after extraction of the reusable ones, verifying which components are present and reachable. Then, the ECs are assessed based on the environmental impacts and economic viability of extracting them from the vehicle, evaluating the thermodynamic rarity indicator and the potential revenue of the material contained in the EC. The potential profit is evaluated by comparing the theoretical revenues that can be generated from the sale of the recovered materials contained in the component with an estimation of the disassembly costs. The indicator is evaluated by the disassembly manager supported by the accounting expert and by the disassembly operator, who provides estimations of disassembly time/cost. It is important to point out that the revenue is influenced by the recycling efficiency. However, being the decision taken in a screening phase, the revenues are estimated considering a theoretical 100% recycling efficiency, i.e., neglecting material losses and quality reduction. The thermodynamic rarity indicator has been identified as a relevant indicator to represent the environmental criticality of the extraction of virgin material. In fact, the indicator allocates a physical value to raw materials in accordance with their scarcity in nature and the net energy required to extract and refine them [26]. The higher the value of thermodynamic rarity of a material, the greater the importance of recovering the material in question.

Fig. 2. Layout matrix mapping the materials of each EC according to thermodynamic rarity indicator [kJ] and revenue [€]

To calculate the two indicators, it is necessary to access the material composition of each EC, i.e., material type and mass content. This information should be provided by EC manufacturer in technical sheet, BOMs or through automotive database, e.g., IMDS (International Material Data System). Based on the values of the two indicators, a layout matrix can be generated for each EC (see Fig. 2), mapping all the materials according to profit potential and thermodynamic rarity.

Once all layout matrices have been constructed, the decision maker prioritizes the extraction of ECs with the highest amount of materials that exhibit both high thermodynamic rarity and profit potential. For this purpose, thresholds for the two indicators are established through the literature review or the experience of the decision-maker. These thresholds define a highlighted area in the Layout Matrix (shown in pink in Fig. 2), delineating a group of materials defined as 'target materials', characterized by high thermodynamic rarity and profit. After the target materials are identified, the decision-makers compares the revenue from these materials to total costs, ranking ECs based on profitability and excluding those not economically feasible. The decision-maker then selects which ECs to extract for further processing. The quantity of ECs to be extracted can be determined by establishing a desired profit margin, ensuring that only those ECs capable of meeting this threshold are selected. In this decision, feedback is gathered on critical issues and possible improvements are collected to inform future eco-design decisions.

The decision-making process is depicted in an information flow diagram (Fig. 3), highlighting inputs, outputs, and feedback loops to ensure effective decision-making and ongoing refinement of material recovery strategies.

Fig. 3. Disassembly and Recycling - information flow of the decision-making moment 1

Decision-making moment 2. The decision-making moment 2 involves determining the disassembly path to extract the chosen ECs from the car with minimal impact. This decision considers destructive disassembly, with the goal of minimizing damage and loss of material without needing to preserve the component's functionalities as in the case of reuse. It is important to highlight that the output of this decision is not an automated disassembly route but rather the optimal route among the ones proposed by the dismantler. Unlikely the high-level screening of Decision 1, this decision and subsequent steps require detailed assessment based on calculated data. The car disassembly manager leads this process, possibly assisted by the disassembly operator and a cost analyst. To support in defining different alternatives of disassembly routes, an analytical tool called "time-based disassembly analysis" [27] can assist in determining the path and disassembly time for each target ECs identified in Decision 1. Then, potential alternative disassembly sequences are defined to extract these target ECs considering the structure of the vehicle. Tools such as the IDIS database [28] which is an information system containing practical information on pre-treatment and dismantling to promote the environmental treatment of ELV, safely and economically and CAD drawings aid in this process. Particular attention must be dedicated to all components with special management requirements, that are encountered during the disassembly process, like liquids, batteries, etc., as in the EU directive on ELV [22].

Once the possible disassembly routes for each EC have been identified, a precedence diagram is constructed to map the disassembly steps and levels and to identify dependencies among components. In this phase, a critical and fundamental step is identifying all the types of liaisons between the material/subcomponents of the EC. Indeed, a standard disassemble time is assigned to each disassembly step based on the liaison type [27] allowing for the calculation of the disassembly time for each path according to the following equation (1):

$$T_e = T_s * \prod_k CF_k \quad (1)$$

where T_s represents the standard disassembly time for the liaison type and CF_k the correction factor of the k_{th} liaison property related to the chosen disassembly conditions. Since the decision focuses on identifying the most cost-effective disassembly route, it is necessary to define the best-performing route based on the disassembly cost. This cost is obtained by multiplying the labour cost and other time-based direct costs by the disassembly time T_e .

Inputs from professional figures and supporting tools are required to execute Decision 2. The outputs from this decision-making process can provide feedback on critical issues encountered during disassembly, informing future design optimizations to minimize disassembly time and associated costs. An information flow diagram (Fig. 4) can guide the decision-making process for efficient disassembly.

Fig. 4. Disassembly and Recycling - information flow of the decision-making moment 2

Decision-making moment 3. The decision-making moment 3 focuses on identifying the most sustainable disassembly route and recycling procedure for extracting and recovering materials from selected ECs. The recycling manager leads this decision, possibly with support from the disassembly operator and a sustainability expert. The objective is to maximize the extraction of materials for recycling while minimizing environmental, social, and economic impacts. For this decision, crucial information is the material composition and design of the component, which can be obtained from IMDS and the CAD of the component.

Starting from the circularity aspect, crucial support can be provided by software tools, such as the commercial software HSC Chemistry Sim® 10 [29] that simulates dismantling, shredding, and sorting processes to determine recoverability and recycling feasibility of a product. To facilitate the assessment of recycling options and to optimise the industrial feasibility of metallurgical recycling processes, all modules, including all materials and compounds of dismantled car parts, are included in the recycling assessment, following a product-oriented approach. If necessary, materials of particular interest, such as ferrous metals, CRMs and organics, can be given special attention, becoming the recycling objective of the simulation to determine the most effective recycling routes for different disassembled car parts.

Consequently, the assessment cases provide guidance on Best Available Techniques (BAT), economically viable industrial recycling treatment routes and the facilities required to achieve the most effective treatment for the different car parts and recycling targets. Due to the complex mix of materials in car parts, it is not possible to define the most appropriate treatment option in advance. Therefore, for each car part, the two or three best options are selected from the metallurgical recycling facilities based on the material composition. The simulation results are: (i) graph showing the main recycling route(s) to be followed according to the recycling objective; (ii) a Material Recycling Flower for each route, showing the Recycling Rate for each individual material; (iii) the total Recycling Rate of a product/part; (iv) the energy recovery (MWh/t feed or per part), exergetic and energy performance.

Besides circularity considerations, it is also crucial to incorporate the sustainability dimension, which entails the environmental, social, and economic assessment of the routes.

Fig. 5. Three-dimensional graph: environmental, economic and social assessment

The impacts are assessed by the sustainability expert, who exploits a sustainability assessment tool such as OpenLCA or similar [30]. The approach is to map the route stages from the HSC tool and create the model in OpenLCA or similar. For environmental assessments, the impacts can be estimated using supporting databases such as ecoinvent [31]. Social impacts, on the other hand, can be assessed using databases such as PSILCA [32], or similar. For economic assessment, the modelling phase consists in the direct estimation of the costs associated with the execution of the routes with the potential revenues from the sale of recycled materials. This step is similar as the one performed in Decision 1, but in this case focuses on the disassembly and recycling of the EC and the information for the estimation are more detailed. After completing all the assessments, the decision-maker can select the optimal disassembly and recycling route based on its performance in the circularity and sustainability pillars. To aid this decision, a tool known as BASF's SEEBalance method [33] enables the visualization of the performance of different recycling routes across the three domains of sustainability through a 3D graphical representation (Fig. 5). Therefore, the alternative with the best performance in all three areas of sustainability is the preferred one to be selected. It may happen that the decision maker chooses to consider only one or two areas of sustainability as a selection criterion, making the graph no longer a 3D but a 2D graph.

In this decision-making moment, the inputs are provided by professional figures, supporting tools and external sources, while the outputs inform other use cases and aid decision-making (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Disassembly and Recycling - information flow of the decision-making moment 3

2) Eco-design Advisory

The Eco-design Advisory methodology supports eco-design phase, aiming to guide designers, identified as the decision-makers, in integrating DfD and DfR principles and creating products with high circular performance. Two decision-making processes are detailed, i.e., the Re-Design decision-making process and the New Design decision-making process, where the decision-maker is the designer. In the Re-Design process, designers are supported in improving existing products, focusing specifically on products that have previously been analysed by the S&C Advisory during the Disassembly and Recycling phases. This approach is grounded in the innovative strategy of the S&C Advisory, which emphasizes the integration of feedback from disassembly and recycling use cases to enhance existing designs. In the New design decision-making process, designers are supported in creating completely new products compliant with eco-design principles.

a) Re-design decision process description

Re-design focuses on resolving conflicts between current product requirements, dictated by the market and strategic business goals, and past design capabilities. The process involves analysing critical issues of existing products, proposing improvements, assessing their feasibility, and verifying actual benefits. The Re-Design decision-making process encompasses four key steps.

Step 1 – Preliminary analysis of the old design. The redesign process starts by analysing feedback obtained from disassembly and recycling decision-makers, pinpointing critical issues emerged from EoL procedures. Moreover, it is fundamental for designers to access critical information from Disassembly and Recycling decision moments: from Decision 1, information like the BOM, the market value of materials, and the value of thermodynamic rarity indicator; from Decision 2, specifics such as the component locations, the disassembly route, cost and time of the component from the vehicle; and from Decision 3, information on recycling routes and performance. As a result, the designer will have a deeper understanding of the component to define optimization to improve the design with a view to disassembly and recycling.

Step 2 – Generation of specific eco-design guidelines with the physics and recycling industry-based approach to Design for Recycling. In this step, the evaluation of improvements in old designs is guided by an approach from both physics and recycling industry. To support the designer, the ten guidelines for DfD and DfR from [34] were chosen for their practicality and applicability across various product types. Moreover, these guidelines are reliable as they have been developed using simulation tools that analyse the relationship between product design and the quality of the resulting recycled materials. Although these guidelines form the basis for Re-Design, they can sometimes be too broad. For this reason, the designer with its expertise can generate specific guidelines for the component under analysis associated to the generic guidelines. Then, feedback collected from disassembly and recycling processes are associated with the specific guidelines, as the guidelines represent a potential solution to the criticality highlighted by the feedback.

Finally, the fulfilment of the guidelines by the old design is evaluated by exploiting a method developed by [35]. This step is fundamental for establishing priority actions, focusing efforts on the guidelines where the product underperforms, prioritizing the guidelines associated with more feedback.

Prioritising the guidelines is recommended but the designer may also decide not to focus on optimising only certain aspects but to implement improvements for all guidelines.

To assess the adherence of the old design to the guidelines, two criteria have been defined: the Margin of Improvement (MI) and the Relevance (R). The MI represents how much improvement is needed in product design in order to comply with the guideline. The design guideline is slightly ($MI = 3$), fairly ($MI = 2$) or fully ($MI = 1$) met in the product design. On the other hand, the R criteria assesses what is the impact of the guideline implementation into product characteristics. In fact, satisfaction of a guideline can generate low ($R = 1$), medium ($R = 2$), or high ($R = 3$) effects on product features, life span, durability, performance etc. As previously mentioned, guidelines that receive more feedback should be prioritized, assigning them the maximum values of MI and R, namely three. The designer has the task of defining MI and R of each guideline, thus enabling the calculation of the Level of Circular Improvement (LCI) of the product and the ranking of guidelines according to LCI. The LCI is calculated multiplying MI and R, and then normalizing this value. Once calculated, a graphical tool such as a radar chart can be exploited in order to help the designer to identify the least satisfying guideline of the product.

Step 3 – Generation of the new design. According to the support provided by the S&C Advisory in previous steps and to the designer experience, a new design can be generated acting on the optimization of the guidelines with high importance.

Step 4 – Comparison amongst the new and old design. A comparative assessment between the new and old designs is conducted based on a set of selected indicators, such as recycling rates, environmental, social, and economic performance indicators. The indicators are assessed through recycling simulation software (HSC tool), sustainability assessment tools like OpenLCA, or specific formulas and are related to the entire life cycle of the product under analysis. The comparison results help designers identify which indicators have improved and where further enhancements are needed.

The information flow diagram (Fig. 7) identifies the primary sources as the outputs of the decision-making stages of dismantling and recycling. Tools such as the HSC tool, OpenLCA and similar evaluate all life cycle phases of the old design, excluding the disassembly and recycling phases, which are already covered by the outputs of the Disassembly and Recycling decisions. These tools are also used to evaluate the new design.

Fig. 7. Re-Design - information flow of the decision-making moment 1

TABLE I. DECISION CARDS

Decision card fields	Decision Card of Disassembly and Recycling			Decision Card of Eco-Design
	Decision 1	Decision 2	Decision 3	Decision 1
Decision	Define which Electronic Component(s) is environmentally and economically beneficial to extract from the car	Define the most cost-effective disassembly route to extract each target electronic component	Determine which combination of disassembly path and recycling process to implement to the EC to recover the maximum amount of material for recycling and generate the least sustainability impacts	Design the Electronic Component from a disassembly and recycling perspective
Decision-maker	<i>Main:</i> Car disassembly manager <i>Supporting:</i> sustainability expert, accounting expert, and the disassembly operator	<i>Main:</i> car disassembly manager <i>Supporting:</i> disassembly operator and cost analyst	<i>Main:</i> recycling manager <i>Supporting:</i> disassembly operator and sustainability expert	<i>Main:</i> Designer
Product focus of the Decision	ECs	Car	ECs	ECs
Supporting tools and technologies	IMDS database	IDIS database	IMDS database; HSC Chemistry Sim® 10; OpenLCA tool, or similar; Ecoinvent, PSILCA database, or similar;	HSC Chemistry Sim® 10 OpenLCA tool, or similar; Ecoinvent database, or similar; PSILCA, HSDB database, or similar
Required Input	3D CAD of the car; List of all ECs in the car and location; BOM of all ECs in the car; Mass of each material contained in the EC [g]; Market value of each material contained in the EC [€/g]; Labor cost and other time-based direct costs for disassembly [€/h]; Estimated disassembly time [h]; Recoverable material [%].	BOM of selected EC; 3D CAD of selected EC; Information from the car manufacturer on car disassembly; Tool needed for disassembly; Number and type of joints; Labor cost and other time-based direct costs for disassembly [€/min]; Estimated disassembly time [h].	BOM of selected EC; 3D CAD of selected EC; Type of materials contained in EC; Material mass [kg]; Market value of materials contained in EC [€/kg]; Labor cost and other time-based direct cost for disassembly [€/h].	Feedback from disassembly and recycling process; BOM of the old design; 3D CAD of the old design; Mass of each material contained in the component [g]; Location of the component in the car; Disassembly time [h]; Disassembly cost [€]; Number and type of toxic materials; Thermodynamic rarity value of each material [kJ/kg]; Recycling rate [%] Energy recovery MWh/t feed or per part]
Environmental indicators	Thermodynamic rarity indicator [kJ]	Not foreseen	14 PEF's midpoint indicators	14 PEF's midpoint indicators
Social indicators	Not foreseen	Not foreseen	PSILCA social indicators	PSILCA or SHDB social indicators
Economic indicators	Resale value per material type [€]; Disassembly cost [€]	Disassembly cost [€]	Resale value per material type [€]; Disassembly cost [€]	Resale value per material type [€]; Disassembly cost [€]
Circular indicators	Estimated disassembly time [h]; Estimated recoverable material [%]	Disassembly time [h]	Disassembly time [h]; Total recycling rate [%]; Recycling rate for individual materials [%]; Energy recovery [MWh/t feed or per part]	Total recycling rate [%]; Recycling rate for individual materials [%]; Energy recovery [MWh/t feed or per part]

b) New-design decision process description

The decision-making process for the development of a new design is slightly different because the component to be analysed does not yet exist. This process is similar to that used for Re-Design but omits steps 1 and 4. The initial step of the new design process corresponds to step 2 of the Re-Design process. However, the guideline classification phase differs because there is no pre-existing design to compare. The final stage, which corresponds to stage 3 of Re-Design process, remains unchanged. In this phase, the designer encounters in an iterative process, making incremental changes to refine and optimise the design.

Table 1 shows all the Decision Cards for all phases. To simplify, only the Decision Card for the Re-Design phase is

described here, as the New Design process is essentially a shortened version of that one.

C. S&C advisory dashboards

In order to provide car manufacturers, OEMs, dismantlers and recyclers with a practical tool meant to guide their decisions and to validate the framework, the advisory methodology here proposed has been implemented to develop an S&C advisory tool. A dashboard for the S&C advisory tool has been prepared for each of the three use cases considered in this work. For each use case, the S&C advisory dashboard provides a dedicated area for the decision-maker to input data and retrieve feedback and information regarding the supported process.

1) Disassembly dashboard

Fig. 8 shows the main interface of the disassembly advisory dashboard, which traces the decision-making process for disassembling the car to extract the EC. Firstly, the identification of which component must be extracted among those contained in the car model is performed (decision-making moment 1). Two are the possible scenarios related to the disassembly evaluation: (i.) the car under analysis has been previously disassembled and information about it is already available, or (ii.) the car has not yet been disassembled and no disassembly information is available because it has not been entered into the software.

In the first scenario, the decision-maker chooses the car model, and a visual representation of the car is displayed, indicating the position of the ECs along with their respective priority ranks for extraction from the vehicle. For each EC, the decision-maker can click on the "Details" button to display information regarding the component's materials, mass [g], recovery rate [%], thermodynamic rarity indicator [kJ], revenue [€] and total cost of the extraction process [€]. In this case, all the data needed to prepare the ranking are already available. In the second scenario, the car model has not previously undergone the disassembly and recycling process supported by the S&C advisory. Consequently, the decision-maker must click on the "Edit" button to input the necessary data for generating the ranking, as depicted in Fig. 9. For each EC within the car, data related to material composition, thermodynamic rarity and revenue are reported in tabular form. The user can then enter the disassembly cost, desired profit margin, and the limiting values of thermodynamic rarity and revenue for each component and access the visual representation of the materials mapped in the revenue-thermodynamic rarity graph. Once this process is completed, the decision-maker can retrieve the visual representation of the car with its classified components in the main advisory interface.

Fig. 9. Disassembly S&C advisory dashboard – “Edit” bottom pop-up

Fig. 10. Disassembly S&C advisory dashboard – “New” bottom pop-up

Knowing the ranking for component extraction, the decision-maker can define the disassembly route to be followed (decision-making moment 2). The S&C advisory proposes the optimal route based on economic performance. At this point, the decision-maker has the option to either proceed with the recommended route or create a new one. If the latter is chosen, the "New" button enables the user to input descriptions of the task, predecessor, and disassembly time for each component to be extracted, as shown in Fig. 10.

During this phase, the decision-maker is tasked with providing information regarding the liaison class, liaison type, and quantity of liaison. Subsequently, an estimate of the disassembly time is calculated for each component, which may vary based on the number and type of liaisons requiring removal. Once the new disassembly route is defined, the S&C advisory determines the optimal one and display it in the main interface.

2) Recycling dashboard

Fig. 11 illustrates the main interface of the Recycling advisory dashboard to determine the disassembly of the EC to extract the material to be recycled and recycling routes to be implemented (decision-making moment 3). To decide on the best combination of disassembly routes and recycling processes, a ranking of the various options in all dimensions of sustainability is created. Through process simulation, the decision-maker evaluates several scenarios, aiming to rank them based on achieving the highest level of circularity, which involves maximizing the percentage of material recovered. In addition, the dashboard provides three further rankings based on social, environmental, and economic impacts. Details of the impacts in these different areas for each route can be viewed by clicking on the 'eye' icon in decision table, which opens a pop-up Fig. 12. This pop-up displays a table listing all the materials, their mass, the recovery rate, the social impact, the economic evaluation, and the environmental impact of the route.

Fig. 8. Disassembly S&C advisory dashboard – main interface

Fig. 11. Recycling S&C advisory dashboard – main interface

Fig. 12. Recycling S&C advisory dashboard – “Eye” bottom pop-up

The recycler has the option to select the optimal route based on a single aspect of sustainability or to consider all areas. A 3D graph is available in the main user interface to illustrate the environmental, economic, and social impacts of the routes in a comprehensive manner.

3) Eco-Design dashboard

Fig. 13 shows the main interface of eco-design S&C advisory dashboard. Considering the Re-Design process, the user is required to specify which EC to optimize in terms of sustainability. The selection may be based on the competitive needs of the company/organization or on feedback collected from disassembly and recycling processes. Once the EC is chosen, the S&C advisory provides the user with a visual representation of the component, along with feedback gathered from the disassembly and recycling decision-making process (step 1). Feedback information is accessed by clicking on a "danger" symbol. Additionally, the designer may require data collected during the disassembly and recycling processes. To facilitate this, two buttons labelled "Go to Disassembly" and "Go to Recycling" are provided. Considering the critical issues identified in the old design, the designer must establish eco-design guidelines (step 2). Once defined, the designer is directed via an "Edit" button, where is evaluated the old design's adherence to these guidelines based on the two criteria of Margin of Improvement and Relevance. From this evaluation, the radar graph is populated, enabling the designer to identify which guidelines require immediate attention.

Fig. 13. Recycling S&C advisory dashboard – main interface

At this point, the designer can proceed with the re-design process (step 3), introducing the solutions implemented in form of advice to be registered in the main interface table. Finally, the designer can compare the old and new designs to assess the improvements achieved (step 4). The comparison, made through selected indicators such as environmental ones in a life cycle perspective. The result of the comparison is shown graphically, through histogram, in the main interface. As already mentioned in the methodological part, the decision-making process for new design results the same as that developed for re-design, excluding steps 1 and 4.

VII. CONCLUSION

The automotive industry, driven by global sustainability and circular economy initiatives, is increasingly focusing on integrating circular and sustainability principles into the entire life cycle of automotive electronics. This paper outlined a comprehensive Sustainability and Circularity advisory framework tailored for automotive electronics industry, aimed at guiding automotive manufacturers, dismantlers, and recyclers through a decision-making process at different life cycle stages, focusing on the BoL in the eco-design phase and the EoL during disassembly and recycling stages.

To develop the framework, the first crucial step was the analysis of the AS IS decision-making process. This involved identifying the types of decisions made during the dismantling, recycling and eco-design phases, the stakeholders involved and the critical issues that need support. Understanding these current practices is essential to ensure the seamless integration of the proposed advisory framework without disrupting existing processes.

Starting from the EoL stages, the S&C advisory framework links the stages of disassembly and recycling, addressing the connection between these processes to improve both the quality and quantity of recovered materials. This connection informs a series of structured decision-making moment, aiming to optimize material recovery (and circularity) and enhance sustainability in the EoL of the ECs. By prioritizing components for extraction, defining efficient disassembly sequences, and selecting the most sustainable recycling routes, dismantlers and recyclers can balance

circular and sustainable considerations effectively. A key innovation in the S&C advisory framework is the integration of a feedback mechanism into the disassembly and recycling decision-making process. This mechanism systematically gathers insights from the actors to identify and document critical challenges and obstacles encountered during the implementation of the decisions. This function of the S&C advisory turns to be crucial for the development of the eco-design decision-making support. The Eco-design Advisory integrates DfD and DfR principles into the eco-design phase, supporting the designers in the Re-Design of an existing EC and the design of completely new EC. In the Re-Design process, the designer starts by analyzing the existing design with input from those responsible for disassembly and recycling. Based on their feedback, the designer draws up eco-design guidelines to implement the suggested improvements. A new design is developed and its effectiveness in improving circularity and sustainability is evaluated against specific performance indicators. This systematic approach ensures that the redesign responds to feedback and advances the goals of circularity and sustainability in the development of ECs. For the design of new products, the process is simplified by using the tool as a support for integrating eco-design principles from the outset.

To support the decision-makers, the S&C advisory framework provide for each use case Decision Cards, which are meant to summarize the different decision moments, detailing the decision to be made, the product focus of the decision, decision-maker, input, supporting tools and indicators for the quantitative evaluations. In addition, information flow diagrams are provided for each decision to determine the source of the inputs required by the S&C advisory. Finally, S&C advisory dashboards have been developed to depict the S&C advisory framework, designing user-friendly interfaces for the three use cases examined in this work. These dashboards represent the base for the development of a real platform, aiming to enhance the knowledge of the decision-makers, retrieve valuable and reliable guidance and register significant issues encountered throughout the processes in the form of gathered feedback from users.

Considering the main output of the AS-IS analysis, the S&C advisory framework is able to address most of the critical issues. In fact, through the disassembly and recycling decision-making process, the dismantlers is able to retrieve all the information needed about the EC, such as the position of components within the car, the composition, etc. being able to define the potential value embedded in the ECs and verify whether this value can cover the disassembly costs. This represents an important support for the dismantler, increasing the extraction of component currently wrongly considered as non-valuable and decreasing the volume of wastes generated, enhancing CE. In addition, the S&C advisory framework plays an important role in supporting dismantlers and recyclers in properly recover precious metal and CRM and incorporating sustainability evaluation in the definition of the recycling routes, which is currently not considered. Other AS-IS critical issues addressed by this work related to design are the features of the framework aiming to provide to the designer all the information and instruments to make choices to improve disassembly and enhance recycling. In addition, the feedback mechanisms address the need for a tool that connects the end of life with the beginning, providing an overview on how much the design influences the EoL.

Despite these innovations, S&C consulting requires further development, including real testing of the framework to validate the described processes and identify potential critical aspects. Since real testing could be time-consuming, the development of surveys or similar tools could be a practical alternative to validate or discover process alternatives. Furthermore, the dependence of the tool on the availability of data could be a challenge, especially in the automotive sector. Overall, the proposed S&C advisory methodology integrated in the presented dashboard offers a valuable tool for decision-making processes and promotes sustainable practices across the automotive electronics industries.

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